

STUDY THE EFFECT OF IRRADIATION WITH A PULSED ND-YAG LASER ON OPTICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract: In this research, the optical properties of nickel ferrite nanoparticles were studied. Samples were prepared by bombarding nickel ferrite alloy with a nema 23 laser with a pulse number of 100 pulses and an energy of 250 millijoules with ethylene liquid. The samples were bombarded for 150-200 pulses and the effect of irradiation on the absorbance, transmittance, reflectivity and absorption coefficient was studied. It was noted that the more the number of pulses increased, the more absorbance increased due to the decrease in the grain size. Also, a decrease in transmittance was noted with an increase in the number of pulses because the relationship between transmittance and absorbance and an increase in reflectivity is that metals increase the reflection of the incident rays on the sample as they provide free electrons that cause an increase in reflectivity and the absorption coefficient increases with an increase in absorbance.

Introduction:

Laser:

LASER is an abbreviation for the English phrase (Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation). Laser is defined as electromagnetic radiation that sends equal amounts of light in terms of frequency and wave phase, which merge with each other to become a light pulse characterized by high energy and strong coherence, and its angle is considered somewhat obtuse, and it depends on stimulating the radiation to be generated, and it is an electromagnetic radiation that consists of photons of equal frequency and identical wavelength, where they interfere constructively between waves to transform into a light pulse with high energy and strong coherence in time and space, and with a very small divergence angle. The laser beam carries thermal energy that exceeds light energy by more than a million times thanks to its compatibility and density, and its thermal effect is limited to the focus on which it is directed. **The most important types of lasers:**

Lasers are classified according to the type of active medium in them, and the large power resulting from them, such as (carbon dioxide laser, which is considered one of the most dangerous types of lasers due to its high power that reaches tens of kilowatts, where it was called death rays, as it is used to cut metals and also in various industrial applications. There are other types of lasers that are very weak, such as those used in daily life in indicators, and these are usually dual-link lasers.

The following are the most important types of lasers

1- Solid-state laser

In this case, the laser material is distributed in a solid matrix, such as the ruby laser and the neodymium-Yag laser

2- Ruby laser

The first laser device was successfully manufactured in 1960 AD, and it was the ruby laser. Ruby is a red crystal consisting of aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) doped with chromium trivalent ions (Cr^{3+}), and the chromium ions are responsible for generating new energy levels within the crystal structure. It is also effective in the transition processes accompanied by laser generation. In the generation tube, a cylindrical crystal is used, and its two opposite ends are cut and coated with silver to form two mirrors of the same material. These two ends form two mirrors, one of which is completely reflective and the other partially reflective.

Figure (1) Laser generation using a crystal

Nedemium Laser:

It is the most common laser for solid-state lasers and its active medium consists of glass that acts as a host medium for the active laser ions, the trivalent nedemium ions and is called the nedemium glass laser. Also, the yttrium aluminum garnet crystal, abbreviated as YAC, acts as a host medium for the nedemium ions Nd^{3+} and the laser is called the nedemium YAC laser. The nedemium ions present in the crystal lattice give multiple transitions, but the most intense one occurs at the transition that has a wavelength equal to 1.064 μm between the energy levels $4f_{3/2} - 4I_{11/2}$. This transition is prohibited according to the selection rules for the electric dipole, so the average lifetime of the upper level of the laser transition is relatively long ($J=0.23$ ms). As for the upper pumping level, it is represented by the group of energy levels that lie above the $4f_{3/2}$ level and the pumping occurs from the ground level $4I_{9/2}$ in two spectral bands around the wavelength (0.8 & 0.73). The multiple levels used for pumping and the use of a wide spectral band photodiode increase the pumping efficiency. The upper pumping levels discharge quickly and with non-radiative transitions to the upper level of the laser transition ($4f_{3/2}$). The lower level of the laser transition ($4I_{11/2}$) also discharges quickly and with non-radiative transitions to the ground level ($4I_{9/2}$). It is clear that the Nd:YAG laser works with a four-level system and is therefore preferred over the ruby laser.

Figure (2) Energy level diagram of the nedmium ion in the yak crystal, the diagram shows the levels related to the pumping scheme and laser transmission.

Nedmium:YAG lasers operate in continuous wave (CW) or pulsed mode and often use an elliptical reflector arrangement to increase the pumping efficiency of a xenon (Xe) lamp.

Figure (3) The usual arrangement of the nedymium laser, where the elliptical reflector is used to increase the pumping efficiency. This laser has many and varied applications, including in metal manufacturing, range determination, and laser surgery. As for the nedymium glass laser, it is used as a laser amplifier in high-power generation systems used in nuclear fusion experiments, where it can give a peak power of more than TW 20 with an energy of about 1.5KJ.

Laser interaction with matter:

The interaction of laser with matter varies depending on the wavelength of the laser beam from one laser to another

The effect of laser energy on matter results from a number of different processes:

1- Thermal effect

Laser energy may be absorbed by colored cells and the result of absorption of the rays is the release of thermal energy. This is the thermal effect of most lasers used.

2- Photochemical effect

The laser interacts with molecules inside the cell and after the interaction between them, chemical changes occur. This is the photochemical effect. An example of this type of laser effect is the injection of some drugs that stimulate photosensitivity into some tissues and the biochemical effect when the drug is stimulated by laser energy.

3- Mechanical effect:

The use of pulses for some high-power lasers may lead to cracking of cellular structures as a result of the occurrence of light and sound waves. This mechanical type is considered an example of the non-thermal effects of the laser.

The light falling from matter interacts with cells through four mechanisms: reflection, refraction, scattering, and absorption

Nickel Ferrite:

Ferrite: A ceramic-like material with magnetic properties that are useful in many electronic devices. Ferrite is a hard, brittle, iron-containing material that is usually black or lead-colored and is polycrystalline, meaning it consists of a huge number of small crystals. It consists of iron oxide bonded to one or more

metals. It is formed by the reaction of iron III oxide with other metals such as magnesium, aluminum, barium, manganese, copper, nickel or even iron itself.

The general formula for ferrite is (MFe_2O_4) where M represents the metal that forms double bonds such as those mentioned above. The chemical formula for nickel ferrite is $NiFe_2O_4$, and manganese ferrite is $MnFe_2O_4$. Garnet contains the rare metal yttrium and its chemical formula is $Y_3Fe_5O_{12}$ and is used in microwave electrical circuits.

One of the most famous ferrites is magnetite, with the chemical formula (Fe_3O_4) . Ferrites have a special type of magnetism known as ferrimagnetism, which differs from the ferromagnetism of some elements such as iron, nickel, and cobalt. In ferrites, the magnetic potential of the atoms that make them up is distributed in two or three different directions, and thus the magnetic field is partially canceled, and thus ferrites become less magnetic than those of ferromagnetic materials. This asymmetry in part of the atomic sites may be due to the presence of two or more types of magnetic ions in the specific crystal structure. The first to use the term ferrimagnetism was the French physicist Louis Néel, who studied ferrites in a systematic manner at the atomic level.

The most important properties of ferrites are high magnetic permeability and high electrical resistance. High permeability is desirable in the field of antenna manufacturing, while electrical resistance is desirable in the field of transformer core manufacturing to reduce the circulating current. Due to the ability of some types of Ferrites absorb microwaves in a specific direction, so they are used in the manufacture of microwave guides

Preparation Methods of Nano material:

The goal in various industrial and technological applications is for the product to be highly efficient, and therefore technical complexity does not stand in the way of reaching chemical materials with high-quality applications and specifications. The physical and chemical specifications accompanying these materials often determine the type and nature of the method used in preparation, although there is a difference between the methods followed in this depending on the economic cost and production capacity of each method. The differences in the use and application of the prepared nanomaterials also represent an important basis for the difference in preparation methods. The increasing demand for these materials since their inception has led steadily to the diversity of methods for producing these materials with superior capabilities at the qualitative and quantitative levels, especially in the industrial fields of electronics, communications, and medical fields, various treatments, and the manufacture of bio-alternatives (for humans, which were impossible to reach or at a huge economic cost. One of the most important common features of all methods is dealing at the atomic scale, one atom towards another, in order to reach a pre-studied design to obtain desired results. The difference in the size scale of the mass of a single material leads to a difference in chemical effectiveness. The smaller the scale, the greater the chemical effectiveness as a result of the increased chemical impact of this material. On this basis, nanoscience and nano-preparation techniques are accelerating steadily according to the stage requirements and the global technical explosion in various sectors. This matter generates great global competition and thus great pressure on the governments of developed countries to continue and reach the best result for the unexpected economic effects resulting from this. The government of the United Kingdom is one example of this. It has formed global research teams according to a two-year timetable and repeated the ball later with another five-year timetable. The results and the level reached have been evaluated. Therefore, taking into consideration all recommendations leading to rapid access to the best production of these materials, which are mostly environmentally friendly materials that do not deplete natural resources and are more economical in various sectors, one example of rapid development is the nano-engine industry.

Samples:

Nickel ferrite alloy was used, 1.5 g of nickel powder and 1 g of iron powder. The powder was mixed and pressed using a hydraulic press in the form of a circular disc. Then the sample was placed in an oven for the purpose of annealing it at a temperature of 1000 degrees Celsius for 4 hours. After that, the sample was left inside the oven until the temperature inside the oven reached room temperature. The alloy was extracted from the oven.

Then, the nickel ferrite nanoparticles were formed by immersing the alloy in ethylene. Nanoparticles (5 ml) of pure ethanol were obtained and bombarded using a nema 23 laser with a wavelength and energy of 250 mJ and a number of pulses (100 pulses). The process was repeated four times. After that, the four samples were bombarded without the alloy: the first sample with 50 pulses, the second with 100 pulses, and the third with 150 pulses. The optical properties of the liquid were studied using a UV-visible spectrometer. 1-2- ND-YAG Laser

Pulsed neodymium yag laser is used for manufacturing, engraving or scraping metals and plastics. It is used in cutting and welding metals, semiconductors and various alloys. Its capacity is (1-5) kilowatts. In its natural state, it has a wavelength of 1064nm. Sometimes the second harmonic wave (frequency doubling) is used with a wavelength of 532nm or the third harmonic wave of 354nm using nonlinear optical materials such as lithium crystal to obtain the visible wavelength of 532nm in green or ultraviolet range. Cesium lithium crystal is used to generate the fourth and fifth harmonic waves.

It is used in the manufacture of nanoparticles using the liquid laser scraping method, where the laser pulse works to uproot atoms from the metal alloy and spread them in the liquid.

Figure (4) UV-Visible Spectrometer

UV-VIS CECILE spectrometer is used to determine the absorbance of light from the sample and can also be used for HPLC (liquid chromatography) detection. The sample is placed to draw the relationship between wavelength and absorbance as the device contains two double beams of light, one is the reference beam and the sample beam that passes through the sample. Some spectrometers contain two detectors to calculate the two beams at the same time. The figure below shows the device.

Absorption:

Figure (3-1) shows the absorbance of nickel ferrite nanoparticles and nickel ferrite after laser irradiation for 50 pulses, 100 pulses, 150 pulses and 200 pulses. We notice that the absorbance increases with the increase

in the number of pulses, as the more the number of pulses increases, the bombarded nanoparticles are fragmented into smaller granular size, and the relationship between intensity and granular size is an inverse relationship, i.e. the more the granular size increases, the absorbance intensity decreases, and if the granular size decreases, the intensity increases, and the reason for the increase in intensity is the increase in electron oscillation, and this increase leads to an increase in absorbance.

Figure (5) Absorption coefficient of nickel ferrite nanoparticles and nickel ferrites after irradiation with laser pulses of 50-100-150-200) pulses.

Permeability:

Figure (3-2) shows the permeability of nano-nickel ferrite and nickel after irradiation with 50 pulses, 100 pulses, 150 pulses and 200 pulses. We notice that the waste decreases as the number of pulses increases. This is because the relationship between permeability and absorbance is an inverse relationship, i.e. if the absorbance increases, the permeability decreases. This is what we notice from the figure. Also, the denser the nanoparticles are, the more they fill the spaces, which leads to a decrease in permeability. During the laser bombardment of nickel, there are some particles that are micro-sized, and when they are cut into laser pulses, this leads to a reduction in the size of the particles and their conversion to nano-sized, and thus the permeability spaces are filled.

Figure (6) The transmittance of nickel ferrite nanoparticles and nickel ferrites after irradiation with laser pulses of (50-100-150-200) pulses.

Absorption coefficient:

Figure (3-4) shows the absorption coefficient of nickel ferrite nano and nickel after irradiation with 50 pulses, 100 pulses, 150 pulses and 200 pulses. We notice that the more the number of pulses increases, the more the absorption coefficient increases, as the absorption coefficient has a direct relationship with the absorbance, and since the absorbance increases as the number of pulses increases, the absorbance increases.

Figure (3-4) Absorption coefficient of nickel ferrite nanoparticles and nickel ferrites after irradiation with laser pulses of (50-100-150-200) pulses.

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